

Hydrazinophosphorus Compounds—V : Reaction of 1,3-Dicarbonyl Compounds with Diarylphosphoro- and Diphenylthiophosphinohydrazides

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1,3-Dicarbonyl compounds (III) reacted with the phosphorus hydrazides to give the corresponding hydrazones. When the hydrazones of ethylacetoacetate were heated at their melting points, they were converted to the corresponding pyrazolin-5-ones. The spectral characteristics of these pyrazolinones were studied.

As the result of an effort^{1,2} to further expand the field of organophosphorus hydrazides chemistry, we wish to report in this paper the reaction of 1,3-dicarbonyl compounds with diarylphosphorohydrazides (I) and diphenylthiophosphinohydrazide (II). The 1,3-dicarbonyl compounds used (III), were acetylacetone benzoylacetone and ethylacetoacetate.

a, Ar=C₆H₅ ;

b, Ar=p-CH₃C₆H₄ ;

a, R=CH₃ ;

b, R=C₆H₅ ;

c, R=OC₂H₅

The hydrazinophosphorus compounds (I, II) behave as a typical hydrazide and react with an equimolar amount of the dicarbonyl compounds (III) to yield the corresponding hydrazones (IV).

P=O absorption of the phosphorohydrazones (IVa-f) appeared around 1200 cm⁻¹^{3a}, while the P=S absorption appeared at 700 cm⁻¹^{3b}.

In 1968, Abramov *et. al*⁴ reported the synthesis of phosphorylated pyrazolin-5-one (Va) from the corresponding hydrazone (IVc). However, Abramov gave no real proof of structure, stating only that the ir spectrum confirmed the structure. In the present study, we have studied the cyclisation of the hydrazones (IVc, f, k) and the structure of the corresponding pyrazolin-5-ones were determined.

The hydrazones (IVc, f, k) on heating at their melting points for one hour without solvent, yielded a colourless viscous oil which solidified slowly when kept at room temperature after trituration with petroleum ether. ¹H NMR spectra of the product pyrazolin-5-ones (Va, b) on comparison with those of the parent hydrazones (IVc, e) revealed the absence of the ethyl alcohol moiety from the spectra of the

	A	R
a-	(C ₆ H ₅ O) ₂ P=O	CH ₃
b-	-do-	C ₆ H ₅
c-	-do-	OC ₂ H ₅
d-	(p-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ O) ₂ P=O	CH ₃
e-	-do-	C ₆ H ₅
f-	-do-	OC ₂ H ₅
g-	(C ₆ H ₅) ₂ P=S	CH ₃
h-	-do-	C ₆ H ₅
k-	-do-	OC ₂ H ₅ ³

Correct analytical data were in support of the structures of these hydrazones (IV). Besides, the ir measurements showed absorption bands around 1600 cm⁻¹ attributed to the C=N stretching. The

pyrazolinones (Va, b). Besides, ³¹P NMR chemical shifts, ir and analytical data (cf. Table 2) are in support of compounds (V). Pyrazolin-5-one (Vc) could not be isolated in analytically pure form.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND CHEMICAL DATA

Compd.	A	R	m p.°C	Formula	%N		%P	
					Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found
IVa	A ₁	CH ₃	82-84	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₄ P	8.09	8.03	8.95	8.73
IVb	A ₁	C ₆ H ₅	102-103	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₄ P	6.86	6.90	7.59	7.60
IVc	A ₁	OC ₂ H ₅	79-80	C ₁₈ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₅ P	7.45	7.40	8.24	8.03
IVd	A ₂	CH ₃	89-90	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₄ P	7.49	7.69	8.28	8.30
IVe	A ₂	C ₆ H ₅	140-142	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₄ P	6.42	6.22	7.11	7.17
IVf	A ₂	OC ₂ H ₅	69-71	C ₂₀ H ₂₅ N ₂ O ₅ P	6.93	6.88	7.70	7.67
IVg	A ₁	CH ₃	200-202	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ N ₂ O S	8.48	8.31	9.39	9.24
IVh	A ₁	C ₆ H ₅	134-135	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ N ₂ OPS	7.14	7.40	7.90	7.80
IVk	A ₁	OC ₂ H ₅	111-112	C ₁₈ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₅ PS	7.77	7.59	8.61	8.40

A₁=(C₆H₅O),P=O A₂=(p-CH₃C₆H₄O),P=O A₃=(C₆H₅)₂P=S

Note : The composition and purity of compounds IVc and IVf were also checked by analysis for C and H.

Compound IVc requires : C, 57.45 ; H, 5.59. Found : C, 57.39 ; H, 5.48.

Compound IVf requires : C, 59.41 ; H, 6.19. Found : C, 59.62 ; H, 6.30.

TABLE 2—IR AND NMR SPECTRAL DATA

Compd.	Ir absorption spectra cm ⁻¹	Nuclear 31P	Magnetic Chemical Shifts, δ _{1H}	Resonance Shifts, δ
Ia	3310 N-H	- 1.61	3.25 (s, NNH ₂ , 2H)	IVf 1600 C=N - 5.7
	1190 P=O		5.25 (d, J _{NH} =35 Hz, NH, 1H)	1190 P=O
	995 P-OAr		7.26 (m, ArH, 10H)	985 P-OAr
Ib	3310 N-H	- 0.06	2.26 (s, CH ₂ , 6H)	1.30 (t, CH ₃ (ester), 3H)
	1200 P=O		3.40 (s, broad, NNH, 2H)	1.80 (s, CH ₂ C=N, 3H)
	990 P-OAr		5.26 (d, J _{PNH} =35 Hz, 1H)	2.30 (s, CH ₂ Ph, 6H)
IVc	1600 C=N	-11.5	1.30 (t, CH ₃ (ester), 3H)	3.35 (s, CH ₂ , 2H)
	1180 P=O		1.80 (s, CH ₂ C=N, 3H)	4.20 (qt, CH ₂ (ester), 2H)
	985 P-OAr		3.30 (s, CH ₂ , 2H)	7.16 (s, ArH, 8H)
IVf	3250 OH	-18.2	1.94 (d, CH ₂ , 3H)	7.25 (d, J _{PNH} =35 Hz, P-NH, 1H)
	1180 P=O		5.44 (d, CH=, 1H)	
	980 P-OAr		7.10 (m, ArH, 10H)	
IVb	3250 OH	-17.3	2.10 (s, CH ₂ , 3H)	
	1185 P=O		2.20 (s, CH ₂ Ph, 6H)	
	970 P-OAr		5.72 (s, CH=, 1H)	
IVd	3250 OH	-18.2	1.94 (d, CH ₂ , 3H)	
	1180 P=O		5.44 (d, CH=, 1H)	
	980 P-OAr		7.10 (m, ArH, 10H)	
IVe	3250 OH	-17.3	2.10 (s, CH ₂ , 3H)	
	1185 P=O		2.20 (s, CH ₂ Ph, 6H)	
	970 P-OAr		5.72 (s, CH=, 1H)	
IVg	3250 OH	-18.2	1.94 (d, CH ₂ , 3H)	
	1180 P=O		5.44 (d, CH=, 1H)	
	980 P-OAr		7.10 (m, ArH, 10H)	
IVh	3250 OH	-17.3	2.10 (s, CH ₂ , 3H)	
	1185 P=O		2.20 (s, CH ₂ Ph, 6H)	
	970 P-OAr		5.72 (s, CH=, 1H)	
IVi	3250 OH	-18.2	1.94 (d, CH ₂ , 3H)	
	1180 P=O		5.44 (d, CH=, 1H)	
	980 P-OAr		7.10 (m, ArH, 10H)	
IVj	3250 OH	-17.3	2.10 (s, CH ₂ , 3H)	
	1185 P=O		2.20 (s, CH ₂ Ph, 6H)	
	970 P-OAr		5.72 (s, CH=, 1H)	
IVk	3250 OH	-18.2	1.94 (d, CH ₂ , 3H)	
	1180 P=O		5.44 (d, CH=, 1H)	
	980 P-OAr		7.10 (m, ArH, 10H)	
IVl	3250 OH	-17.3	2.10 (s, CH ₂ , 3H)	
	1185 P=O		2.20 (s, CH ₂ Ph, 6H)	
	970 P-OAr		5.72 (s, CH=, 1H)	
IVm	3250 OH	-18.2	1.94 (d, CH ₂ , 3H)	
	1180 P=O		5.44 (d, CH=, 1H)	
	980 P-OAr		7.10 (m, ArH, 10H)	
IVn	3250 OH	-17.3	2.10 (s, CH ₂ , 3H)	
	1185 P=O		2.20 (s, CH ₂ Ph, 6H)	
	970 P-OAr		5.72 (s, CH=, 1H)	
IVo	3250 OH	-18.2	1.94 (d, CH ₂ , 3H)	
	1180 P=O		5.44 (d, CH=, 1H)	
	980 P-OAr		7.10 (m, ArH, 10H)	
IVp	3250 OH	-17.3	2.10 (s, CH ₂ , 3H)	
	1185 P=O		2.20 (s, CH ₂ Ph, 6H)	
	970 P-OAr		5.72 (s, CH=, 1H)	
IVq	3250 OH	-18.2	1.94 (d, CH ₂ , 3H)	
	1180 P=O		5.44 (d, CH=, 1H)	
	980 P-OAr		7.10 (m, ArH, 10H)	
IVr	3250 OH	-17.3	2.10 (s, CH ₂ , 3H)	
	1185 P=O		2.20 (s, CH ₂ Ph, 6H)	
	970 P-OAr		5.72 (s, CH=, 1H)	
IVs	3250 OH	-18.2	1.94 (d, CH ₂ , 3H)	
	1180 P=O		5.44 (d, CH=, 1H)	
	980 P-OAr		7.10 (m, ArH, 10H)	
IVt	3250 OH	-17.3	2.10 (s, CH ₂ , 3H)	
	1185 P=O		2.20 (s, CH ₂ Ph, 6H)	
	970 P-OAr		5.72 (s, CH=, 1H)	
IVu	3250 OH	-18.2	1.94 (d, CH ₂ , 3H)	
	1180 P=O		5.44 (d, CH=, 1H)	
	980 P-OAr		7.10 (m, ArH, 10H)	
IVv	3250 OH	-17.3	2.10 (s, CH ₂ , 3H)	
	1185 P=O		2.20 (s, CH ₂ Ph, 6H)	
	970 P-OAr		5.72 (s, CH=, 1H)	
IVw	3250 OH	-18.2	1.94 (d, CH ₂ , 3H)	
	1180 P=O		5.44 (d, CH=, 1H)	
	980 P-OAr		7.10 (m, ArH, 10H)	
IVx	3250 OH	-17.3	2.10 (s, CH ₂ , 3H)	
	1185 P=O		2.20 (s, CH ₂ Ph, 6H)	
	970 P-OAr		5.72 (s, CH=, 1H)	
IVy	3250 OH	-18.2	1.94 (d, CH ₂ , 3H)	
	1180 P=O		5.44 (d, CH=, 1H)	
	980 P-OAr		7.10 (m, ArH, 10H)	
IVz	3250 OH	-17.3	2.10 (s, CH ₂ , 3H)	
	1185 P=O		2.20 (s, CH ₂ Ph, 6H)	
	970 P-OAr		5.72 (s, CH=, 1H)	

- a, A = (C₆H₅O)₂P=O ; a, Ar = C₆H₅ ;
 b, A = (p-CH₃C₆H₄O)₂P=O ; b, Ar = p-CH₃C₆H₄
 c, A = (C₆H₅)₂P=S

Interestingly, pyrazolin-5-ones (Va, b) exist predominantly in the OH-tautomeric form (V') which is stabilised by a hydrogen-bonded chelated ring. This is supported by the absence of the C=O absorption in the ir spectra and the appearance of a band at about 1485 cm⁻¹ due to the group C=C-OH. The ¹H NMR shows also signals at δ 11, 13 for (Va) and (Vb) due to the -OH respectively.

Di-*p*-tolylphosphorohydrazide (Ib) was prepared by the reaction of the corresponding chloride with a benzene suspension of hydrazine hydrate and was characterised as a hydrazide by conversion into a number of aldehyde and ketone derivatives (VI), (p-CH₃C₆H₄O)₂P(O)NHN=CRR'.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Beckman IR-5A unit as KBR pellets. ¹H NMR spectra were obtained with Jeol-100 and EM-390 spectrometers in DCCl₃. ³¹P NMR spectra were measured on Jeol JNM-FX 60 Fourier Transform NMR spectrometer and shifts are given in ppm. Positive values are downfield from the reference (85% H₃PO₄).

Di-*p*-tolylphosphorohydrazide (Ib) :

Over a 2 hr. period, (0.1 mole) of di-*p*-tolylphosphorochloride in 25 ml. benzene was added with stirring to a suspension of (0.25 mole) 95% hydrazine in 100 ml. benzene. The mixture was then refluxed for 3 hr, cooled and filtered. The colorless solid was washed with water and then crystallised from ethanol. m.p. 125°.

Anal. Calcd. for C₁₄H₁₇N₂O₅P : C, 57.53 ; H, 5.82 ; N, 9.59 ; P, 10.62. Found : C, 57.41, H, 5.74, N, 9.78, P, 10.70.

In the preparation of the hydrazones (IV, VI), the hydrazides (0.01 mole) was boiled under reflux with the appropriate carbonyl compound (0.01 mole) in ethanol (50 ml) for 2 hr. The hydrazones generally separated from the cool concentrated solution and were recrystallised from ethanol. Analysis and ir spectral data supported the structures (IV, VI).

TABLE 3—PHYSICAL AND CHEMICAL DATA

Compd.	R	R'	m.p.°C	Formula	%N		%P	
					Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found
VIa	C ₆ H ₅	H	132-133	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₅ P	7.36	7.11	8.15	8.10
VIb	p-ClC ₆ H ₄	H	158-159	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₅ ·P·Cl	6.76	6.79	7.47	7.44
VIc	m-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	H	150-151	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₅ P	9.88	9.92	7.29	7.40
VId	p-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	H	161-162	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₅ P	9.88	9.89	7.29	7.45
VIe	o-HOC ₆ H ₄	H	178-180	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₅ P	7.07	6.91	7.83	8.01
VI f	p-HOC ₆ H ₄	H	170-171	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₄ P	7.07	6.90	7.83	8.05
VIg	p-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	H	182-184	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₅ P	6.88	6.93	7.56	7.30
VIh	C ₁₀ H ₇	H	124-125	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₅ P	6.51	6.33	7.20	6.99
VII	C ₁₄ H ₉	H	158-159	C ₂₂ H ₂₅ N ₂ O ₅ P	5.83	5.90	6.46	6.60
VIk	CH ₃	CH ₃	154-155	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₅ P	8.43	8.54	8.20	8.30

Preparation of the Pyrazolin-5-ones (V) :

Acetylacetone hydrazones (IVc, f,k) (1 g.) were heated at their melting points for 1 hr and then allowed to cool. The viscous oil was triturated with petroleum ether and left for 12 hr, whereby a crystalline precipitate was formed. It was removed by filtration and crystallised from ethanol. The pyrazolin-5-one of compound (IVk) did not crystallise out and all the trials to isolate it in analytically pure form failed.

m.p° : Va, 114-115 ; Vb, 123-124.

Anal. Calcd. for Va $C_{16}H_{15}N_2O_4P$: C, 58.18 ; H, 4.54 ; N, 8.48 ; P, 9.39. Found : C, 58.24 ; H, 4.39 ; N, 8.51 ; P, 9.22.

Calcd. for Vb $C_{18}H_{19}N_2O_4P$: C, 60.34 ; H, 5.31 ; N, 7.82 ; P, 8.66. Found : C, 60.41 ; H, 5.25 ; N, 7.79 ; P, 8.61.

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